

Societal & Political Engagement
of Young People in Environmental Issues

D1.7: Minutes of 4th Advisory Board meeting

WP1 – Project Management

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Contributions from				

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2.0	06/12/17	Final	Minor comments by partners	Ms Roxana Nica, Mr Francesco Mollace

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Table of Contents

D1.7: Minutes of 4th Advisory Board meeting

1	Executive summary	4
2	Introduction	4
3	Update of the EEAB list	4
4	EEAB activities.....	5
5	Feedback and actions.....	5
6	Conclusions	8
	ANNEX A - Members of the EEAB.....	8
	ANNEX B – STEP EEAB update (November 2017).....	9

1 Executive summary

The current deliverable is the fourth report on the activities of the STEP project's External Expert Advisory Board (EEAB). The members of the EEAB were contacted either through physical meetings or via Internet. This deliverable summarizes the recommendations that these experts have provided to the project consortium from M23 (April 2017) until M30 (November 2017). During the previous months of the project implementation, several activities with the members of the EEAB have been organized and the feedback gained was reported in the deliverables D1.2, D1.5 and D1.6.

Regarding the structure of the current document, in Chapter 2 a short introduction on the EEAB role within the STEP project is provided, while in Chapter 3 any changes made on the board from M23 until M30 are presented. The meetings held during this period between EEAB members and STEP partners are presented in Chapter 4, and, finally, some of the most important recommendations of the experts to the STEP partners are summarized in Chapter 5 accompanied with the actions taken by the consortium to address these points.

2 Introduction

The EEAB is a counselling body established to provide advice and guidance where is needed for the development of the project. Besides the communication between the STEP partners, it is very important to convey ideas, research and outcomes of the project to relevant stakeholders, to receive their feedback, and make sure that the final outcomes of the project are aligned with the vision of potential users. In order to achieve that, an External Expert Advisory Board (EEAB) has been established early in the project (M3) to review the project activities and outcomes, identify the strong and weak points with respect to the objectives of the project, and provide recommendations during all the project phases.

The STEP EEAB consists of a group of excellent professionals in diverse relevant fields as well as members of potential user groups.

3 Update of the EEAB list

The EEAB list may be updated throughout the duration of the project in case a new need for consultation will emerge. In addition, as the STEP EEAB members are people who are engaged with various activities in their fields of expertise, they may change position during the project.

For the given period (April 2017 – November 2017), the following changes were made on the Board:

Efthymios Altsitsiadis joined the STEP EEAB

Dr. Altsitsiadis is a research expert at the Research Group Marketing at the KU Leuven. He was the manager of CONCORD, the largest EU initiative on consumer science and is currently partner in CIPTEC, working on the consumer engagement and behavioural insights efforts. He is teaching branding at the masters programme and his personal research interests lie at the intersection of consumer behavior and social innovation. Efthymios is a stark advocate for user-centricity and has a passion for advancing behaviourally informed policy.

Among his other appointments, Efthymios is a fellow at the academy of the think-tank OpenForum Europe (Google, IBM, Oracle, Deloitte and Redhat) that promotes openness in the ICT sector and a visiting professor at the health department of University of St Mark & St John where he gives lectures on selected topics. Efthymios is also a board member of the social research consultancy White Research where he advises the citizen centric applied research in areas like community energy, smart cities, agro-technologies.

The full list of the EEAB members can be found in ANNEX A - Members of the EEAB, while short CVs of all members are also provided in the [STEP website](#).

4 EEAB activities

During these 30 months of the STEP project, the consortium has kept a continuous and fluent communication with the members of the EEAB. All the contacted members gave valuable feedback which was reported in the deliverables D1.2, D1.5, D1.6.

For the given period (April 2017 – November 2017), the following activities took place, so that the consortium could acquire feedback from the EEAB members:

- *Epaminondas Christofilopoulos, Greek National Contact Point for Horizon 2020 for Environment, Energy and Transport* was in close cooperation with Christodoulos Keratidis and Maria Vogiatzi all these months. A number of meetings took place at the premises of DRAXIS. Epaminondas provided consultation to the STEP team for the EU pilot and assisted the team in setting up all EU dialogues.
- *Kerstin Franzl, as the Coordinator of the EUth project* and with extensive experience in public participation had a meeting with Christodoulos Keratidis in October, as well as 2 online meetings during the previous months.
- *Lorenzo Floresta, Coordinator of the International Youth Panel of the Horizon 2020 project CATCH-EyoU* joined STEP's 6th project meeting, which was held in Siderno (Italy) on May 2017.
- Maria Vogiatzi and Christodoulos Keratidis held two meetings with Efthymis Altsitsiadis, one at DRAXIS premises and one in Brussels. The purpose of the meetings was to explore the viewpoint of a potential user about the STEP platform and to discuss new ways of user engagement.

The feedback that was acquired from the EEAB members during the above activities is presented in the following Chapter.

5 Feedback and actions

This Chapter focuses on the most important remarks pointed out during the activities described in Chapter 4 and provides additional information for each activity.

1) *Epaminondas Christofilopoulos:*

Epaminondas supported the STEP team with the implementation of the EU dialogue from the very beginning. Prior to the launch of the EU pilot Maria and Christodoulos had a brainstorming session with Epaminondas, in order to develop a comprehensive pilot plan with interesting topics that will arouse the interest of young European citizens. Within this framework the three dialogues below have been uploaded onto the STEP platform (in consultation with YEE).

- 17 Sustainable Development Goals. Which are more important to you?
- Tackling Climate Change
- Air Quality

Apart from his contribution in the setting of the dialogues, Epaminondas suggested to the STEP team to contact some organizations that could support the promotion of the dialogues. In particular, he proposed the organizations below:

- UN SDSN Youth (17 Sustainable Development Goals dialogue)
- Little sun foundation (Tackling Climate Change dialogue)
- Climate Change Week (Tackling Climate Change dialogue)
- Global Greengrants Fund (Tackling Climate Change dialogue)

<The STEP team took into account Epaminondas comments and proposals. Additionally, the team contacted the organizations proposed by Epaminondas.>

2) Kerstin Franzl :

Based on her experience acquired from the EUth project, Kerstin pointed out that partners organizing public participation processes should not be involved in pilots unless the ICT tools for e-participation are fully functional and tested. A tool under development is naturally not mature - but the public is annoyed to be confronted with technical difficulties. Thus the testing should rather be done internal until the tool is almost ready. Only then the public can be involved as final testers.

There are two main factors for raising turnout of citizens in public participation processes:

1. Interest of participants on the issue that is put under participation. Young people are much more interested in participating in a public participation procedure if the issue is relevant to them. If the procedure is not a real public participation procedure, but a demonstration of an ICT tool, they lose their interest.
2. The rate of participation is higher if young people are familiar with the concept of participation, i.e. if they have already experienced other participation projects and got the feeling that their voices really count; building this kind of trust is a time-demanding process.

There are few significant differences in public participation of young people and adults. One basic difference is that young people want to see the prompt reaction of the policy makers and that the results of the participation process are being implemented directly.

<DRAXIS communicated these remarks to the partners and to each STEP pilot individually during the monthly calls. >

3) Lorenzo Floresta:

During STEP's meeting in Siderno Lorenzo Floresta, the new member of STEP Advisory Board made a presentation on how to engage youth in policy making & how public authorities could come closer to young people. Lorenzo stressed the importance of the youth workers in the engagement of young people in the society and policy making. Additionally, he presented the European path for the years 2001 – 2018:

- 2001 (White Paper on Youth) Open Method of Coordination in Youth
- 2005 European Youth Pact approved by the Council of the European Union to achieve the objectives of the Lisbon Treaty on growth and the fight against youth unemployment
- 2006 Introduction of Structured Dialogue as an Open Consultation Model for Young People.
- 2010-2018 «EU Youth Strategy» approved by the Council of Youth Ministers in the light of the 2008 economic and social crisis.

<After his presentation, Lorenzo had the chance to discuss with all partners, especially the pilots and provide them with useful information on the topic of e-participation. Since Lorenzo is from Italy, he suggested some contacts to STEP's Italian pilot partner.>

4) Efthymis Altsitsiadis:

Two meetings were held between Efthymis, Christodoulos and Maria. During the meeting the STEP team presented in detail the STEP project and the platform and an extensive discussion on STEP's engagement strategy followed. Efthymis noted that from a young user's perspective, the graphical identity and the interface of the platform are quite attractive, which is necessary, but not sufficient to engage citizens. He pointed that public authorities should update the content of the platform regularly, upload interesting public dialogues and always inform the citizens on how they will use the results of the dialogues. According to Efthymis, community participation could be an effective policy-making tool, but time is needed in order to build trust between young people and the authorities. A basic pillar of the process is that, when Municipalities decide to carry out public dialogues the roles must be clarified and no false expectations should be generated. Additionally, all the opinions should be respected and actions should be taken according to the results of the public dialogue. Finally, Efthymis suggested that a variety of awards could be used as incentives to motivate users to participate in public dialogues.

<The members of the consortium were informed about the discussion with Efthymis and they decided to award active youth participation with a trip to STEP's final event. Within this framework, two young citizens from each STEP pilot will travel with the STEP team to Berlin and participate in STEP's final event.>

Table 1: Indicative feedback and STEP actions

Name	Recommendations/ remarks/Activity	STEP WP
Epaminondas Christofilopoulos	Consultation for the EU pilot	WP5, WP7
Kerstin Franzl	The STEP platform should be fully functional and tested before its official launch.	WP3, WP5
Kerstin Franzl	Public dialogues should be interesting for the users	WP5
Lorenzo Floresta	Recommendations to pilot partners	WP5
Efthymis Altsitsiadis	Awards could be used as incentives to motivate users to participate	WP5

6 Conclusions

Since the very beginning of the project, the STEP consortium was in close collaboration with the External Experts Advisory Board (EEAB) members were individually contacted whenever a consultation for the project's progress was needed. Especially, some of the members of the EEAB were in close collaboration with the STEP team and actively supported project's activities. The present document presents the activities taken place with the STEP EEAB during the last 8 months (from April 2017 until November 2017), before the project's completion, the feedback acquired from the experts, and the actions that the STEP consortium took to address these recommendations.

ANNEX A - Members of the EEAB

Name	Location	Position	Personal website
Ms. Kerstin Franzl	Berlin, Germany	Coordinator of the project EUth	http://goo.gl/LuTtRe
Dr. Catriona Macaulay	Edinburgh, UK	Head of User Research and Engagement at The Scottish Government	https://www.linkedin.com/in/catmacaulay
Dr. Enric Coll Gelabert	Barcelona, Spain	Environmental Technician at Environmental Education and Promotion Office of the Barcelona Provincial Council	-
Mr. Epaminondas Christofilopoulos	Thessaloniki, Greece	Horizon 2020 National Expert for Climate Change	https://goo.gl/clZ1Yc
Dr. Eva Lievens	Leuven, Belgium	Professor of Law and Technology at the Law Faculty of Ghent University	https://goo.gl/khIO_MZ
Mr. Joakim Jardnberg	Helsingborg, Sweden	Internet and Social Media Expert at Helsingborg	https://goo.gl/OuKGAQ
Ms. Eva Theisz	Stockholm, Sweden	Deputy Director of International Affairs at the Swedish public employment service	https://goo.gl/2LXkL3
Ms. Christiane Klemm	Greifswald, Germany	Board Member of Youth and Environment Europe	http://goo.gl/hUibce
Mr. Babis Tsitlakidis	Brussels, Belgium	DG CONNECT, Unit of eHealth and ICT for Wellbeing and Ageing	https://goo.gl/ogFR6y
Mr. Lorenzo Floresta	Caserta, Italy	Coordinator of the CATCH-EyoU project	-
Mr. Efthymis Altsitsiadis	Brussels, Belgium	Research expert at the Research Group Marketing at the KU Leuven	https://be.linkedin.com/in/efthymios

ANNEX B – STEP EEAB update (November 2017)

A quick overview of 2017

After almost 30 months of implementation the **STEP project is slowly reaching its end on December 2017!**

Since the beginning of 2017 all STEP pilots have been promoting the platform to the youngsters of their area. The pilot's dissemination activities were based on a comprehensive Local Dissemination Strategy, which was enriched by each pilot according to the local needs. All STEP pilots organized **workshops, launch events** and a number of additional online and offline dissemination activities in order to engage youngsters, maximize citizens' participation and get useful feedback from the users.

The STEP platform was officially launched to the public on **March 2017** and since then all pilots have been uploading public dialogues. Young citizens living at the pilot areas were invited to visit the platform, get informed on local environmental issues and express their opinion.

In order to fully exploit the STEP solution, the STEP team decided to use it at Pan-European level and address all European young citizens. In this framework the STEP platform was presented to the **Chairwoman of the Environment, Public Health and Food Safety Committee of the European Parliament (ENVI Committee)**, Mrs Adina-Ioana VĂLEAN. Additional meetings followed with the ENVI Committee and even though Mrs Adina-Ioana VĂLEAN was interested in the STEP solution, at that point of time the ENVI Committee can not take advantage of the STEP platform.

Committed to the initial goal, we decided to implement the EU pilot on it's own! ©
On July 2017 we launched the EU pilot and uploaded the first public dialogue!

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The STEP platform

The STEP platform

The STEP platform was ready since the beginning of the year and a number of updates took place within the previous months based on the feedback that was gathered by the users.

The Social Media Mining Tool

A new UI has been developed for the Social Media Mining Tool. As part of this new UI, we have streamlined navigation, so as create a more intuitive, inviting and concrete interface.

The mobile apps

STEP is also available in the Google Play and the App Store. Search for it as step.green

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Each pilot has a different story to share with us!

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.12 Meet the STEP pilots...

6 Pilots from 4 Countries + 1 EU pilot

Valdemoro City, Spain

Mollet del Vallès, Spain

Association of the Communities of Locrie area, Italy

New Entry!!! Resilient Thessaloniki

Region of Crete, Greece

Hatay Metropolitan Municipality, Turkey

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Mollet del Valles pilot

- ✓ **2.368** citizens participated in 21 public dialogues
- ✓ **Most successful dialogue in Mollet:**
“Select a project; make your allocation of 100.000 euros of public investment. Participative budget.”

The purpose of this dialogue was to establish a participative process and enable citizens to take decisions about public investments in Mollet del Vallès. Citizens participated massively and proposed a variation of projects to be implemented. Participants had to vote 1 out of 9 possible projects to be funded and implemented, as well as propose one of their own. Given the high number of participants and the small difference in terms of votes between the first and the second project, the Municipality decided to go forward with both of them! It should be noted that following this dialogue, an additional participatory budgeting dialogue was uploaded on the STEP platform.

- ✓ **Basic conclusion for Mollet del Vallet from STEP experience:**
“The more you’ll open your decision-making procedures the bigger will be the engagement of your citizens”.

Association of Communities of Locride Area pilot

✓ **1.681** citizens participated in 8 public dialogues

✓ **Most successful dialogue in Locride:**

“Waste water treatment: Let’s clean the sea in Locride Area”

One of most important environmental issues in Locride Area is the waste water treatment and the pollution of the sea. The Association created this dialogue, so as to collect the best ideas and petitions with the purpose to open a discussion with the decision makers for a different approach in waste water treatment and to place the best proposals, in the political agenda.

✓ **A success story in Locride:**

Within the framework of STEP the Municipality of Sant’Agata del Bianco decided to amend the Municipality’s statute in order to encourage and facilitate the participation of young people in decision making processes. lowering the age limit for submitting a petition

On the 28th April 2017, the Municipal Assembly approved two changes in the statute:

- Reduce the age limit for participating in a petition from 18 to 16 years old
- Reduced the number of required signatures for initiating a petition

✓ **Basic conclusion for Locride from STEP experience:**

“You need the active support of a youth core group – (youth leaders) to engage young people”

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Metropolitan Municipality of Hatay pilot

✓ **3.070** citizens participated in 14 public dialogues

✓ **Most successful dialogue in Hatay:**

“What should be done for a greener Hatay and a better Eco-friendly city?”

According to Hatay, this dialogue was one of the most successful in terms of young citizens engagement and participation. The Municipality of Hatay managed to gather many posts with different proposals, which have been promoted to the respective departments according to the content.

✓ **A success story in Hatay:**

Because of the citizens’ increased complains on the STEP platform about the deficient municipal solid waste management, the Municipality decided to bring forward the plans initially foreseen for the upcoming months and take the appropriate measures earlier.

✓ **Basic conclusion for Hatay from STEP experience:**

“In order to engage young citizens in e-participation you need a simple and easy to answer dialogue, so that all citizens can participate and express their opinion.”

Region of Crete pilot

✓ 1209 citizens participated in 43 public dialogues

✓ Most successful dialogue in Crete :

“The protection of Caretta-Caretta in Crete”

The dialogue was created to provide the users general information about the legal framework for the protection of the seaturtles *Caretta Caretta*. The dialogue was developed with the support of Archellon, a NGO that is active in Crete. Users were invited to answer a questionnaire and post their ideas and suggestions on measures and actions that could strengthen the protection of *Caretta-Caretta*. The respondents showed that they are familiar to the problems and aware of the legislative framework and of the actions needed to be implied by local businesses and from the Region of Crete. The feedback gathered was discussed at a meeting between the Department of Environment and Hydroeconomy of Chania-Rethimno, the Department of Environment of Heraklion and Archellon, in order to develop and coordinate a strategy for the upcoming year.

✓ Basic conclusion for Crete from STEP experience:

“In order to engage young citizens, you need to bring under public consultation attractive dialogues”

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Valdemoro pilot

✓ 288 citizens participated in 8 public dialogues

✓ Most successful dialogue in Valdemoro:

“We care for our parks”

The scope of creating this dialogue was trifold:

- to inform and motivate the citizens in retaining the city parks clean
- to increase citizens awareness of the city park flora and fauna
- to involve citizens and youths in a fruitful discussion about supplementary actions and incentives that could be given in order to retain city parks clean and valuable to all. A

All citizens posts were forwarded to the Department of the Environment that will discuss these proposals and relative actions within the local government.

✓ Basic conclusion for Valdemoro:

Involving and engaging citizens in e-participation is a quite difficult and time-demanding procedure

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Thessaloniki Pilot

✓ **212** citizens participated in 1 public dialogue

✓ *The additional pilot of Thessaloniki:*

An additional pilot, not foreseen initially in the project has joined the STEP pilots. This is a success story for our project, since the Municipality of Thessaloniki decided to implement the pilot with using their own resources.

There is only one dialogue uploaded on the platform so far, so there are no results available from Thessaloniki's STEP experience.

EU Pilot

✓ **402** citizens participated in 3 public dialogues

✓ *3 EU dialogues uploaded so far:*

- "17 Sustainable Development Goals. Which are more important to you?"
- "Tackling Climate Change"
- "Air Quality"

The purpose of these dialogues is to inform young European citizens about important environmental issues and to ask them to raise their voice and express their opinion.

Following the closure of each dialogue, a report is being prepared and sent to relevant NGOs agencies, etc.

The "Air Quality" dialogue is still open!

You are invited to participate and share the dialogue with friends or your network of contacts

<http://step.green.eu>

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STEP Final Event

STEP celebrates 30 months of active Youth Participation in environmental decisions!

STEP will host its final event on the 8/12/2017 within the [EUth Open Summit "Youth eParticipation in Europe: The Future is now"](#), which will take place on 7-8/12/2017. The STEP team will present the experience gained, the final version of the platform and results generated from 30 months' work!

In order to award active youth participation, each STEP pilot has implemented a contest through the STEP platform that gave as a unique prize a trip for two young people to Berlin.

12 young people coming from the STEP pilot areas have been granted with a trip to join STEP final event and elaborate on their experience, ideas and perceived value of eParticipation!

